

Initial Assessment of a Microwave Imaging System for Continuous Monitoring of Liver Tumor Ablation

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Summary:

In this work, the in-silico assessment of a microwave imaging device specifically designed for liver ablation monitoring is presented. The outcomes of this study show the designed device is capable of providing 3D images of the ablated region, paving the way for the next stage in which the device will be implemented and experimentally assessed in the same conditions as those simulated in this study.

Abstract:

1. Introduction

Microwave thermal ablation is a treatment that can effectively eradicate liver tumors, with a significant impact on clinical practice. However, the treatment's effectiveness is heavily dependent on the experience of the clinician and would improve if paired with an image-guidance device for treatment monitoring [1]. Conventional imaging modalities, such as computed tomography, ultrasound, and magnetic resonance imaging, show some disadvantages, motivating interest in alternative technologies. In this framework, microwave imaging was recently proposed as a potential candidate, being capable of implementing real-time monitoring by means of low-cost and portable devices [2]. In this work, the in silico assessment of a microwave imaging device specifically designed for liver ablation monitoring is presented.

2. Methods

The main design guidelines for the microwave imaging system for liver ablation were given in [3], where the optimal working frequency (0.5-2 GHz), the coupling medium ($\epsilon_r = 23$, $\sigma = 0.07$ S/m), and the antennas were adopted. For the in-silico assessment of this device, an imaging experiment involving eight Vivaldi antennas in an array configuration and a 3D-printable phantom mimicking the post-ablated liver was simulated. The geometry of the scenario is shown in Figure 1(a). The phantom is a simple structure made of two nested ellipsoids, the outer ellipsoid mimics the coagulation necrosis region and the inner ellipsoid represents the carbonized tissue, shown in Figure 1(b). The imaging step was carried out using a differential MWI approach similar to the one used in [2], which exploits the distorted Born approximation (DBA) [4] and allows for real-time imaging results. To supply the data needed by the differential imaging procedure, both the scenario with and without the phantom was simulated. The input data to the imaging procedure were given by the difference between the two simulated data sets. The simulated scattering parameters were corrupted with an additive Gaussian noise with SNR = 45 dB, which is consistent with the noise floor in a real experimental environment. The imaging results are given in terms of the 3D normalized maps of the amplitude of the retrieved contrast function (which expresses the variation of the permittivity with respect to the host medium) within the imaged volume. Due to the introduced approximation, the images are not quantitative, but only convey qualitative results on the portion of the region where a variation of permittivity is occurring.

3. Results

The obtained MWI reconstructions are shown in Figure 1 (c), where the cross-sections along the z-axis (i.e., moving from the antenna towards the phantom) are shown. To improve readability, the contour of the phantom was superimposed on the reconstruction in the relevant cross-sections. The maps are more intense (dark red) where the permittivity variation is expected to occur. As such, they allow estimating the start of the ablated region with an accuracy of about 6mm as far as the portion of the region facing the antennas is concerned. Conversely, a slight underestimation of the ablated region is experiencing in the not-illuminated side. As far as the resolution in the direction of the antennas array (x-axis) the size of the region is quite accurately retrieved. Conversely, the reconstruction has a low resolution in the y-axis.

Figure 1 (a) The experimental setup; (b) the phantom structure; (c) MWI reconstructions for the phantom as slices in the x-y plane for various values of z. In the panels, the x-axis is the horizontal axis, and the y-axis is the vertical one.

4. Conclusion

This study is meant at providing a numerical assessment of the performance of the MWI device to monitor thermal ablation designed in [3]. The outcomes suggest that the designed device is capable of providing 3D images of the ablated region, although with some limitations especially as far as the resolution along the y-axis and the imaging of the not illuminated side of the ablated region are concerned. To counteract these effects different antennas arrangement will be considered. The results of this further analysis together with the initial experimental activities involved in the designed system and phantom will be presented at the conference.

Reference

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